

ECOLOGICAL ASSESSMENT OF THE CENOPOPULATIONS OF SOME SPECIES OF IRISES IN THE GANJA-GAZAKH REGION

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Abstract

The increasing anthropogenic impact on the places of natural growth of plant communities leads to the fact that the population of wild ornamental irises decreases from year to year. The aim of the study is to determine the limiting environmental factors affecting the distribution of certain species of irises (*Iris* L) in the Ganja- Gazakh region. The assessment of the potential and real ecological valence of species was carried out, the coefficient of ecological efficiency and the tolerance index of species were calculated. With the help of amplitude ecological scales, it is possible to determine the state of the growing environment in the response of the cenopopulation to changes in certain environmental factors. It was revealed that the species of irises growing on the territory in the Ganja- Qazakh region. Are assemblers in the structure of ecological and cenotic groups, and changes in the soil and climate of the region can be determined by their condition in the cenopopulation. The results of the research can be used in phyto-indication of territories and monitoring of plant resources.

Keywords: Potential Ecological Valence, Climatic, Soil Factors, Ecological Scales.

INTRODUCTION

To determine the environmental conditions changing as a result of anthropogenic impact on ecosystems, it is productive to use the phytoindication method. The phyto-indication method makes it possible to assess changes in the environment less costly than using measuring instruments and laboratory studies. (Didukh, Y., Vasheniak, I., & Bednarska, I. (2022)., Gamrat, R., & GAŁCZYŃSKA, M. (2021)., Glibovytska, N., & Mykhailiuk, Y. (2020)., Kunakh, O. M., Lisovets, O. I., Yorkina, N. V., & Zhukova, Y. O. (2021)., Tsyganov, D. N. (1983).)

Vegetation is the most directly observable component of it, sensitively reacting to all changes in soils, rocks, groundwater, minerals, etc. (27). (Tsyganov, D. N. (1983).)

Due to the relationship of plants with environmental factors, it is possible to determine not only the needs of plants, but also to determine the state of the ecotope plants. Simply put, use vegetation cover as an indicator of environmental conditions.

The adaptation of vegetation and even populations of individual species to climatic and soil factors makes it possible to apply bioindication methods and compile regional ecological scales. (Vikto-rov, S. V., & Remezova, G. L. (1988)., Zverev, A. A. (2020).)

With the help of amplitude ecological scales, it is possible to determine the limiting factors affecting the spread of plants, such as illumination, variable humidification, temperature regime, nitrogen richness of soils, soil acidity, and salt regime. The ecological analysis makes

it possible to correctly assess the role of cenopopulations in the vegetation cover for planning further work on biodiversity conservation and reintroduction of endangered species (26) (The Red Book of the Republic of Azerbaijan. Rare and endangered species of plants and fungi. Second edition. (2013)).

MATERIAL AND METHODS

The object of research was the rhizomatous species of irises growing in the Ganja-Qazakh region. Some types of irises (*Iris* L) are rare and are listed in the Red Book of Azerbaijan. (Ibadullayeva, S. J., & Huseynova, I. M. (2021), Nurlana, N. (2021).)

Rhizomatous irises – ephemeroïds have highly decorative qualities (Grossheim, A.A. (1940)., Roguz, K., Gallagher, M. K., Senden, E., Barlev, Y., Lebel, M., Heliczer, R., & Sapir, Y. (2020)) because of which they are subjected to haphazard collection by the population, but the main reason for their decrease is the anthropogenic impact on the places of their growth – the use of territories for growing crops, an increase in urban territories, recreational zones, haphazard grazing (in early spring, agricultural trample the places of growth of rare species of irises). (Askerova, L. A. (2019).)

Geobotanical descriptions were made to study the cenopopulation and ecology of some species of the genus *Iris* L growing on the territory of the western part of Azerbaijan. Transects were established, and the sizes of transects varied from the location of the cenopopulation. The type of vegetation, the class and group of formations, the degree of tiering, the projective cover, and the degree of distribution and abundance of phytocenoses in which species of irises occur were clarified. (Ipatov, V. S. (1997).)

To identify the effect of environmental factors on the range of endurance of rhizomatous irises, the method of amplitude scales by D. N. Tsyganov was used. (The Red Book of the Republic of Azerbaijan. Rare and endangered species of plants and fungi. Second edition. (2013), Zhivotovsky, L. A., & Osmanova, G. O. (2021).)

Amplitude scales contain estimates of all conditions in which the species occurs, and are expressed by the amplitude (scope) of gradations of the environmental factor. (Ipatov, V.S. (1997).)

To analyze the characteristics of environmental factors, the following parameters were taken: thermoclimatic (TM), climate continentality scale (KN), ombroclimatic aridity-humidity scale (OM), cryoclimatic scale (Cr), soil moisture (Hd), soil salt regime (Tr), soil nitrogen richness scale (Nt), soil acidity scale (Rc), variable soil moisture scale (fH), illumination–shading scale (Lc). (The Red Book of the Republic of Azerbaijan. Rare and endangered species of plants and fungi. Second edition. (2013), Viktorov, S. V., & Remezova, G. L. (1988).)

Taking into account the scale of D.N. Tsyganov, the method of assessing the potential and real ecological valence of L.A. Zhukova's species was used. (Dorogova, Yu.A., Zhukova, L.A., Turmukhametova, N.V., Gavrilova, M.N., & Polyanskaya, T.A. (2010)., Kosolapova, N.V., Gudovskikh, Y.V., Egoshina, T.L., Kislitsyna, A.V., & Luginina, E.A. (2021, November),

Viktorov, S. V., & Remezova, G. L. (1988.)

Ecological valence is defined as the adaptation of a species to environmental factors in a particular range. For qualitative assessment of a certain ecological factor, the potential ecological valence (PEV) of a species is considered as a mechanism for adapting changes in the ecological factor in the cenopopulation. (Dorogova, Yu.A, Turmukhametova, N.V., & Zhukova, L.A. (2019), Dorogova, Yu. A., Zhukova, L. A., Turmukhametova, N. V., Gavrilova, M. N., & Polyanskaya, T. A. (2010)., Viktorov, S. V., & Remezova, G. L. (1988).)

The potential ecological valence of a species is considered an adaptation of the cenopopulation only to a certain ecological factor. (Dorogova, Yu.A, Zhukova, L.A., Turmukhametova, N. V., Gavrilova, M. N., & Polyanskaya, T. A. (2010).)

In the course of the study, the real ecological valence of this cenopopulation in the phytocenosis was calculated by the formula:

The environmental efficiency coefficient is calculated as a percentage of the REV/PEV ratio to each environmental factor as an indicator of the ecological potential of the species: (Dorogova, Yu. A., Zhukova, L. A., Turmukhametova, N. V., Gavrilova, M. N., & Polyanskaya, T. A. (2010).)

$$\text{Koeff.ec.eff.} = \frac{REV}{PEV} \times 100\% \quad (1)$$

In a certain phytocenosis, several environmental factors simultaneously interact with plants, but the needs of plants in each environmental factor are different. The influence of several factors on a species determines the tolerance coefficient (index) (Ti). The tolerance index (Ti) is determined by whether a particular species is affected by general factors:

$$Ti = \frac{\sum PEV}{\sum scale} \quad (2)$$

where: PEV is the potential ecological valence, and REV is the realized ecological valence.

If the tolerance index (Ti) of a species is high, then there is a high probability of the spread of the cenopopulation in various ecological zones. (Dorogova, Yu. A., Zhukova, L. A., Turmukhametova, N. V., Gavrilova, M. N., & Polyanskaya, T. A. (2010).)

Based on the research results, it is possible to monitor the ecological state of the environment, cenopopulation, and species diversity.

RESULTS

5 studied species of rhizomatous irises by thermoclimatic factors (Table 1.) (TM) (*Iris lineolata* (Trautv) Grossh.; *I. camillae* Grossh., *I. schelkownikowii* Fomin; *I. annae* Grossh.; *Iris grossheimii* Woronow ex Grossh) are stenovalent, 2 species (*Iris alexeenkoi* Fomin; *I. iberica* Hoff) hemistenovalent, 2 species (*Iris germanica* L, *I. pseudacorus* L) – mesovalent.

According to the climate continentality scale (K N), 7 species (*Iris alexeenkoi* Fomin; *I. lineolata* (Trautv) Grossh.; *I. camillae* Grossh.; *I. schelkownikowii* Fomin; *I. annae* Grossh.;

Meyer; *Iris grossheimii* Woronow ex Grossh.; *I. iberica* Hoff) are stenovalent, 2 species (*Iris germanica* L, *I. pseudacorus* L) – mesovalent. This is an indicator that 7 stenovalent species are not tolerant to changes in the conditions of the continental climate.

Table 1 : Potential and Real Ecological Valences (REV, REV), Ecological Efficiency Coefficient (Ek.ef. ef.), and Tolerance Index (TI) of the Studied Species According to D.N.Tsyganov Climatic Scales

N	Species	TM			KN			OM			Cr			TI
		PEV	REV	Ek.ef. koef.	PEV	REV	Ek.ef. koef.	PEV	REV	Ek.ef. koef.	PEV	REV	Ek.ef. koef.	
1	<i>Iris germanica</i> L	0,58	0,53	91,3	0,61	0,53	88,3	0,61	0,5	88	0,42	0,3	83	0,55
2	<i>I.pseudacorus</i> L	0,47	0,29	87,2	0,66	0,6	90,9	0,53	0,5	87	0,53	0,5	87	0,55
3	<i>I.alexencoii</i> Fomin	0,23	0,17	73,9	0,26	0,13	50	0,13	0,1	46	0,2	0,1	65	0,20
4	<i>I.lineolata</i> (Trautv) Gross	0,35	0,29	82,8	0,2	0,13	65	0,33	0,3	100	0,2	0,1	65	0,27
5	<i>I.camillae</i> Gross	0,35	0,29	82,6	0,33	0,26	78,88	0,33	0,3	79	0,27	0,2	74	0,32
6	<i>I.shelkownikowii</i> Fomin	0,24	0,29	82,9	0,33	0,3	79	0,33	0,3	79	0,27	0,2	74	0,32
7	<i>I.iberica</i> Hoff	0,35	0,24	75	0,33	0,3	82	0,4	0,3	83	0,27	0,2	74	0,31
8	<i>I.annae</i> Gross	0,35	0,35	82,9	0,33	0,3	79	0,4	0,3	83	0,2	0,1	65	0,32
9	<i>I.grossheimii</i> Woronow ex Gross	0,35	0,35	82,9	0,33	0,3	79	0,4	0,3	83	0,2	0,1	65	0,32

According to the ombroclimatic scale (OM), 5 studied species (*Iris lineolata* (Trautv) Gross; *Iris alexencoii* Fomin, *I. camillae* Gross, *I. shelkownikowii* Fomin; *I. grossheimii* Woronow ex Grossh.) are stenovalent, 2 species (*Iris annae* Gross, *I. iberica* Hoff) are hemistenovalent; 1 species (*Iris pseudacorus* L) is mesovalent, 1 species (*Iris germanica* L) is hemievalent.

According to the indicators of the cryoclimatic scale (Cr), 7 studied species of irises (*Iris alexencoii* Fomin, *I. lineolata* (Trautv) Grossh. *I. camillae* Grossh., *I.shelkownikowii* Fomin; *I. iberica* Hoff, *I. annae* Grossh, *Iris grossheimii* Woronow ex Grossh.) are stenovalent, 1 species (*Iris germanica* L) – hemistenovalent, 1 species (*Iris pseudacorus* L) – mesovalent.

Thus, all climatic factors (TM, KN, OM, Cr) for the species of irises common in this territory are limiting. This affects the competitiveness of price populations during a period of small climate changes, which leads to a decrease in the number of populations.

To determine the potential ecological valence, the factors of the scale soil moisture content (Hd), soil acidity (Rc), soil nitrogen richness (Nt), salt regime (Tr), soil moisture variability (fH), as well as illumination-shading (Lc) of the territory were used. (Table 2).

According to the soil moisture scale (Hd), 8 species of irises (*Iris germanica* L, *I. lineolata* (Trautv) Gross, *I. alexencoii* Fomin, *I. camillae* Gross, *I.shelkownikowii* Fomin, *I. iberica* Hoff, *I. annae* Groos, *Iris grossheimii* Woronow ex Grossh), 1 species (*I. pseudacorus* L) are stenovalent, 1 species (*I. pseudacorus* L) is mesovalent. Thus, according to the scale of soil moisture, all types of irises common in this territory are stenovalent.

According to the scale of the salt regime of soils (Tr) 8 species of irises (*Iris germanica* L, *I. lineolata* (Trautv) Gross, *I. alexeencoii* Fomin, *I. camillae* Gross, *I. shelkownikowii* Fomin, *I. iberica* Hoff, *I. camillae* Gross, *I. annae* Gross, *Iris grossheymii* Woronow ex Grossh) They are stenovalent and only 1 species (*Iris pseudacorus* L) is hemistenovalent.

According to the scale of soil nitrogen richness (Nt), 5 species of irises (*Iris shelkownikowii* Fomin; *I. lineolata* (Trautv) Gross; *I. camillae* Gross; *I. annae* Gross; *I. grossheymii* Woronow ex Grossh) are hemistenovalent, 2 species (*Iris alexeencoii* Fomin, *I. iberica* Hoff) are stenovalent; 1 species (*Iris germanica* L) – hemievalent, 1 species (*Iris pseudacorus* L) – mesovalent. The species of irises growing on this territory can also adapt to less nitrogen-rich soils.

According to the soil acidity scale (Rc), 2 species (*I. alexeencoii* Fomin, *I. shelkownikowii* Fomin) are stenovalent, 6 species (*Iris germanica* L, *Iris lineolata* (Trautv) Grossh, *Iris camillae* Grossh, *Iris iberica* Hoff, *I. Annae* Grossh., *Iris grossheymii* Woronow ex Grossh.) are hemistenovalent and only 1 species (*I. pseudacorus* L) is eivalent.

According to the scale of soil moisture variability (fH), 4 common species (*Iris alexeencoii* Fomin, *I. lineolata* (Trautv) Gross, *I. annae* Gross, *I. grossheymii* Woronow ex Grossh, *I. pseudacorus* L) are stenovalent, 3 species (*I. alexeencoii* Gross, *I. camillae* Gross, *I. shelkownikowii* Fomin) hemistenovalent.

According to the indicators of soil scales, the adaptability of common irises to the arid zone is confirmed.

Most common species of irises are adapted to well-lit areas. According to the illumination-shading scale (Lc), 2 species of irises (*Iris alexeencoii* Fomin, *I. iberica* Hoff) are stenovalent, 7 species (*Iris germanica* L, *I. lineolata* (Trautv) Gross, *I. camillae* Gross, *I. shelkownikowii* Fomin, *I. annae* Gross, *I. grossheymii* Woronow ex Grossh) – hemistenovalent, 1 species (*Iris pseudacorus* L) – mesovalent, According to the indicators of this scale, the species common in this territory are light-loving, some are common on the edges of the forest.

Table 2: Potential and Real Ecological Valences (REV, REV), Ecological Efficiency Coefficient (Ek.ef. ef.), and Tolerance Index (TI) of the Studied Species According to the Soil Scales of D. N. Tsyganov

N	Species	Hd			Tr			Nt			Rc			fH			TI
		PEV	REV	Ek.ef. koef.													
1	<i>Iris germanica</i> L	0,3	0,2	81	0,2	0,2	71	0,6	0,5	86	0,4	0,3	79	-	-	-	0,3
2	<i>I.pseudacorus</i> L	0,5	0,4	91	0,6	0,5	91	0,5	0,5	83	1	0,9	92	0,5	0,4	67	0,62
3	<i>I.alexeevcoi</i> Fomin	0,3	0,2	81	0,2	0,2	71	0,3	0,2	56	0,2	0,2	65	0,3	0,2	67	0,26
4	<i>I.lineolata</i> (Traut) Gross	0,3	0,3	87	0,2	0,2	71	0,5	0,4	80	0,4	0,3	79	0,3	0,2	67	0,34
5	<i>I.camillae</i> Gross	0,3	0,2	81	0,2	0,2	71	0,5	0,4	80	0,4	0,3	79	0,4	0,3	75	0,36
6	<i>I.shelkownikowii</i> Fomin	0,3	0,2	81	0,2	0,2	71,4	0,4	0,4	93	0,3	0,2	65	0,4	0,3	75	0,32
7	<i>I.iberica</i> Hoff	0,3	0,2	85	0,2	0,2	76,2	0,3	0,2	67	0,3	0,2	77	0,4	0,3	75	0,30
8	<i>I.annae</i> Gross	0,3	0,3	87	0,2	0,2	71,4	0,5	0,4	80	0,4	0,3	79	0,3	0,2	67	0,30
9	<i>I.grossheymii</i> Woronow ex Gross	0,3	0,3	87	0,2	0,2	71,4	0,5	0,4	80	0,4	0,3	79	0,3	0,2	67	0,34

DISCUSSION

Thus, it was found that in the ecological and cenotic groups of the western region of Azerbaijan, the species of irises have a narrow distribution area. There are almost no eurybiont species here, and their ability to spread is limited. Stenobiont species are relatively predominant.

According to the indicators of the climatic scale (*Table 3*), stenobiont species predominate (78%). There is a relatively small percentage of mesobiont species (22%).

According to the indicators of the soil scale, the iris species common in the territory are mainly hemistenobionts (56%). Stenobiont species make up 44%, stenobiont, and eurybiont species do not occur.

Table 3: Tolerance Index (Ti) and Ecological Niche of Iris Species Depending on Climate, Soil, and Illumination

N	Species	Climatic factors		Soil factors		Illumination factors	
		Ti	Ecological niche	Ti	Ecological niche	Ti	Ecological niche
1	<i>Íris germanica</i> L	0,55	Mezobiont	0,30	Stenobiont	0,44	Mezobiont
2	<i>Íris pseudacorus</i> L	0,55	Mezobiont	0,62	Hemievri-biont	0,55	Mezobiont
3	<i>Íris alexeencoii</i> Fomin	0,20	Stenobiont	0,26	Stenobiont	0,33	Stenobiont
4	<i>Írislineolata</i> (Trautv) Grossh.	0,27	Stenobiont	0,34	Hemisteno-biont	0,44	Mezobiont
5	<i>Íriscamillae</i> Grossh.	0,32	Stenobiont	0,36	Hemisteno-biont	0,44	Mezobiont
6	<i>Í. Shelkownikowii</i> Fomin	0,32	Stenobiont	0,32	Stenobiont	0,44	Mezobiont
7	<i>Íris iberica</i> Hoff	0,31	Stenobiont	0,30	Stenobiont	0,33	Stenobiont
8	<i>Íris annae</i> Grossh.	0,32	Stenobiont	0,34	Hemisteno-biont	0,44	Mezobiont
9	<i>Íris grossheymii</i> Woronow ex Grossh	0,32	Stenobiont		Hemisteno-biont	0,44	Mezobiont

According to the scale of illumination of the territory, stenobiont species make up 78%, mesobiont 22%. On the other hand, there are no eurybiont species.

CONCLUSION

As a result of the research, it was found that according to the indicators of the climatic and soil scale, rhizomatous species of irises in the western region of Azerbaijan have a very narrow range, are adapted to their distribution sites and the tolerance of these species is low. They have adapted only to the ecological conditions of growth, and a change in one of the environmental factors limits their spread. It can be said that most of the iris species common here have small distribution areas due to their steno- and hemistenovalence. Since these species are considered to be assemblers, they have little effect on the structure of the ecological-cenotic groups in which they are distributed. It belongs to rare and endangered species for the region and needs special protective measures.

References

- 1) Abramova, L. M., Shirokikh, P. S., Golovanov, Ya. M., Mustafina, A. N., & Kryukova, A.V. (2019). On the ecology of rare steppe species of the genus *Iris* in the Southern Urals. *Bulletin of Tomsk State University. Biology*, (48), 56-72.
- 2) Abramova, L. M., Shirokikh, P. S., Golovanov, Ya. M., Mustafina, A. N., & Kryukova, A.V. (2019). On the ecology of rare steppe species of the genus *Iris* in the Southern Urals. *Bulletin of Tomsk State University. Biology*, (48), 56-72. DOI: 10.17223/19988591/48/3
- 3) Askerova, L. A. (2019). The ecological valence of some species of irises in the western part of Azerbaijan. *Bulletin of Science and Practice*, 5(10), 50-55. [https://doi.org/ 10.33619/2414-2948/47/06](https://doi.org/10.33619/2414-2948/47/06)
- 4) Didukh, Y., Vasheniak, I., & Bednarska, I. (2022). Phytosociological and ecological peculiarities of Host in Ukraine. *Hacquetia*, 21(2), 235-252. <https://doi.org/10.2478/hacq-2022-0004>
- 5) Dorogova, Yu. A., Zhukova, L. A., Turmukhametova, N. V., Gavrilova, M. N., & Polyanskaya, T. A. (2010). *Ekologicheskiye shkaly i metody analiza ekologicheskogo raznoobraziya rasteniy* [Ecological scales and methods of analysis of ecological diversity of plants]. (in Russian)
- 6) Flora Azerbajdžana [Flora of Azerbaijan] (1853). Baku, Ed AN Azerbajdžan. SSR, vol. I-VIII, 195 [in Russian]
- 7) Gamrat, R., & Gałczyńska, M. (2021). Flora diversity of field forest patches in landscapes with varied geomorphological units and land use in Poland. *Appl. Ecol. Environ. Res*, 19(2), 1473-1489. http://dx.doi.org/10.15666/aecr/1902_14731489
- 8) Glibovytska, N., & Mykhailiuk, Y. (2020). Phytoindication research in the system of environmental monitoring. *Ecological Sciences*, 1(28), 11-14. <https://doi.org/10.32846/2306-9716/2020.eco.1-28.16>
- 9) Grossheim, A. (1940) *Flora Kavkaza* [Flora of Caucasus], ed. 2, 2. Izdatel'stvo AzFAN, Baku, 284 pp. (in Russian)
- 10) Ibadullayeva, S. J., & Huseynova, I. M. (2021). An Overview of the Plant Diversity of Azerbaijan. *Biodiversity, Conservation and Sustainability in Asia: Volume 1: Prospects and Challenges in West Asia and Caucasus*, 431-478. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-59928-7>
- 11) Kiseleva, L. L., Silaeva, J. G., & Parakhina, E. A. (2019). Ecological assessment of the habitats of *Carexbrizoides* L. on the eastern border of the area. *Socio-ecological Technologies*, 9(4), 395-413. DOI: 10.31862/2500-2961-2019-9-4-395-413
- 12) Kosolapova, N. V., Gudovskikh, Y. V., Egoshina, T. L., Kislitsyna, A. V., & Luginina, E. A. (2021, November). To The Characteristic of Cenopopulations *Dactylorhiza Dactylorhiza Fuchsii* (Druce) Soo of the Middle and Southern Taiga. In *IOP Conference Series: Earth and Environmental Science* (Vol. 901, No. 1, p. 012025). IOP Publishing DOI: 10.13057/biodiv/d230903
- 13) Krinitsyn, I. G., & Lebedev, A.V. (2019). Ecological characteristics of the habitats of cenopopulations of heart-shaped linden and common spruce in the Kologrivsky Forest Reserve. *Nature Management*, (3), 121-126. DOI: 10.22363/2312-797X-2023-18-3-373-384
- 14) Kunakh, O. M., Lisovets, O. I., Yorkina, N. V., & Zhukov, Y. O. (2021). Phytoindication assessment of the effect of reconstruction on the light regime of an urban park. *Biosystems diversity*. 29(3), 276-285. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.15421/012135>
- 15) Nazarenko, N. N., Pokhlebaev, S. M., Malaev, A.V., Tretyakova, I. A., & Khodzhaev, A. K. (2020). Ecological and cenotic groups of vascular plant flora of the Orenburg region and phytoindication of biotopes. *SamaraScientificBulletin*, 9(4 (33)), 109-120. DOI: 10.17816/snv202094117

- 16) Polyanskaya, T.A., & Dorogova, Yu.A. (2010). Ecologicheskoye raznoobraziye raznih jznennih form rasteniy borealnoy ecologo-senoticheskoy gruppi. [Ecological diversity of various plant life forms of the Boreal ecological-cenotic group.] *Proceedings of the Samara Scientific Center of the Russian Academy of Sciences*, 12(1-3), 804-807. (in Russian)
- 17) Prokopyeva, K. O., Konyushkova, M. V., Novikova, N. M., & Sobolev, I. V. (2021). Digital phytoindication of soil salinity in dry steppes (Republic of Kalmykia). *Arid Ecosystems*, 11(2), 173-185. DOI: [10.1134/S207909612102013X](https://doi.org/10.1134/S207909612102013X)
- 18) Red book of the Republic of Azerbaijan. Rare and endangered plant and fungi species. (2013) Second edition. Baku.
- 19) Roguz, K., Gallagher, M. K., Senden, E., Bar-Lev, Y., Lebel, M., Heliczer, R., & Sapir, Y. (2020). All the colors of the rainbow: Diversification of flower color and intraspecific color variation in the genus *Iris*. *Frontiers in Plant Science*, 11, 569811.
- 20) Tsyganov, D.N., (1983). Fitoindikaciya ecologicheskikh rejimov v podzone hvoyno-listvennih lesov. [Phytoindication of ecological regimes in the subzone of coniferous-deciduous forests] Nauka, Moscow. (in Russian)
- 21) Viktorov S.V., Remezova G.L., (1988) Indikacionnaya geobotanika. [Indicative geobotany] Moscow: Publishing House of the Moscow University. (in Russian)
- 22) Zhivotovsky, L. A., & Osmanova, G. O. (2021). Fitoindikatsionniy indeks raznoobraziya usloviy sredy. [Phyto-index of diversity of environmental conditions]. *Biology Bulletin*, 48, 207-213. (in Russian) DOI:[10.31857/S0002332921020156](https://doi.org/10.31857/S0002332921020156)
- 23) Zverev, A. A. (2020). Methodological aspects of using indicator values in biodiversity analysis. *Contemporary Problems of Ecology*, 13, 321-332. DOI:[10.1134/S1995425520040125](https://doi.org/10.1134/S1995425520040125)